

Recommended citation: Gumaelius, L., Lee, Y., Morimura, K., & Kolmos, A. (2017). The Role of Entrepreneurial Skills in Engineering Education: A Case Study Performed in Denmark, Japan, Korea and Sweden . In Quadrado, J. C., Bernardino, J., & Rocha, J. (Eds.), *Education Excellence for Sustainability. SEFI 45th Annual Conference* (pp. 594-602). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Azores, Portugal. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14698191.

The role of entrepreneurial skills in engineering education: A case study performed in Denmark, Japan, Korea and Sweden

L. Gumaelius¹

Associate professor

KTH, School of Education and Communication in Engineering Sciences

Stockholm, Sweden

E-mail: lenagu@kth.se

Y. Lee

Research professor

Korea University, Center for teaching and learning

Seoul, South Korea

E-mail: eduist@korea.ac.kr

K. Morimura

Professor

University of Tokyo, Institute for Innovation in International Engineering

Education

Tokyo, Japan

E-mail: morimura@t-adm.t.u-tokyo.ac.jp

A. Kolmos

Professor

Aalborg University,

Aalborg, Denmark

E-mail: ak@plan.aau.dk

ABSTRACT

The importance of teaching entrepreneurial skills has been on the agenda for several years. But how do engineering education institutes (EEl)s serve as institutions facilitating the learning of these skills? In this study, we compare four EEl)s from four countries located in two global regions, East Asia and the Northern Europe, in order to identify models for how education in entrepreneurship can be implemented according to each country's situation. We use a modified version of Dahlöf and Lundgren's frame-factor theory to analyse how the universities understand the internal and external driving forces for the development of this kind of education. We also address how these frame factors affect the development processes at each EEl. The study identifies differences in these processes, which depend on how pressures originating outside the universities are expressed.

Conference key areas: skills and engineering education

Keywords: entrepreneurship, innovation, frame-factor theory, engineering-education institutes

¹ Corresponding Author, L. Gumaelius, lenagu@kth.se

INTRODUCTION

Globalisation, the digitalisation of society and other trends are expected to lead towards a different work situation for many people. A more turbulent work environment is expected, where more short-term jobs and project-oriented jobs are created and where people change work tasks more often.

This is one reason entrepreneurship has been on the agenda in education development for the past 20 years. Already at the beginning of the 1990s, OECD (the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) published a report that pointed to entrepreneurial skills as a crucial ability for people who wanted to pursue continuous technical development (Blanchflower & Oswald 1998).

However, the entrepreneurship and enterprise are difficult to define. The entrepreneurship concept has its origin in an economic tradition and is derived from the French word *entreprendre*, which refers to an active person who gets things done. The Oxford Dictionary defines an entrepreneur as someone who 'sets up a business or businesses, taking on financial risks in the hope of profit'. Recent literature has extended this concept to cultural and social contexts (Skolverket 2015). A broader approach is also taken by Shane and Venkataraman (2000), who explained that entrepreneurship involves discovery, invention, creativity and, of course, ways of bringing the new ideas into a market. In an effort to cover all aspects of entrepreneurship, we refer to the general capabilities associated with entrepreneurship as 'entrepreneurial skills' and to the special capability of knowing how to establish a business as 'knowledge about enterprise'.

Over the past 20 years, enterprise education and the training of entrepreneurial skills have been the subject of a great discussion and debate in OECD countries. Strategic plans for entrepreneurship education at different levels of the educational system have been developed in some countries (Regeringskansliet 2009, Ministeriet för Vitenskap etc. 2010). Engineering-education institutes (EEl) play an important role in entrepreneurial development; engineers often have positions in which entrepreneurship is a highly regarded skill, because they work in areas where technical development is moving very fast. The last 10 years have witnessed the formation of centres for entrepreneurship and enterprise and professorial appointments at engineering universities. These academic developments are meant to ensure that entrepreneurship is fully realised at the university level.

However, there is a lack of empirical studies that address how engineering education actually provides entrepreneurial education for engineers in a structured way. Although we have seen many examples of entrepreneurship courses, our impression is that entrepreneurship is not always taught in a coordinated, strategic and continuous fashion.

In this study, we take the first steps towards creating a model that can inspire and help EEl to develop strategic and coordinated programmes for the teaching of entrepreneurial skills and enterprise. The model will be based on our comparison of cases from four countries representing two OECD regions. The case comparisons address how the EEl in these countries include

entrepreneurial skills and enterprise in their education. The two global regions in which the EEIs are located are very high-tech regions, but they are significantly different with respect to both educational and work culture.

The comparison will be conducted by analysing how engineering faculty, including both management and teachers, interpret the integration of entrepreneurial skills and enterprise from a university perspective. The analytical approach is based on the frame-factor theory. The results will be used to develop models for how engineering education can become a strong link in the engineer's development of entrepreneurial skills.

1. BACKGROUND

1.1 The frame-factor theory

In this study, our perspective resembles the classic frame-factor theory, developed by Dahlöf and Lundgren in the 1960s and 70s (Broady, 1999). They used this theoretical framework to analyse the factors influencing teachers' teaching situations.

This theory posits that a teacher's ability to influence a teaching situation is relatively limited and is controlled by a variety of external factors that are difficult to change directly. Although we do not use the theory as such, it serves as an effective basis for our approach to the development of the teaching of entrepreneurship. We investigate the process of educating entrepreneurial citizens not through the eyes of the teacher, but through the eyes of the EEIs. The frames are seen as the factors of entrepreneurship education that EEIs cannot directly influence. These factors are defined in terms of each country (in this case each EEI) in order to create an awareness of which factors constrain the development of entrepreneurial-skills education at specific EEIs.

We investigate the processes undertaken? at each EEI to implement and run entrepreneurial or enterprise education. By studying the combination of these two types of factors, we hope to explain how and by whom the educational-development processes in this area are controlled.

In our approach, the *frames* are understood as the laws and regulations that affect entrepreneurship education and that enable engineering education. The *processes* refer to what is going on at the universities, such as faculty-training programmes, the development of strategic plans and the creation of good preconditions for the teaching of entrepreneurial skills and enterprise. The *result* is a student who has learned the skills necessary for becoming an entrepreneurial engineer (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: An overview of the described aim of the study.

Different Frame factors:

2. METHODS

Two professors from the engineering faculty of each EEI were selected as informants for the survey. The EEIs studied were Aalborg University (AAU), Denmark, University of Tokyo (UT), Japan, Korea University (KU), South Korea, and the Royal Institute of Technology (KTH), Sweden.

In total, eight informants were included in the survey. One of the informants, the dean of an engineering department/college, represented high-level management. The other informants were professors engaged in the work of entrepreneurship education. A risk of the study was that the selected informants represented a group that had significantly greater competence in entrepreneurship education than other faculty members.

The faculty members were interviewed according to a semi-structured interview technique, in which a questionnaire was used as the question base. Each interview lasted about an hour.

Our analysis of the interview transcripts focused mainly on the questions associated with the frames and the processes taking place at each EEI.

3. RESULTS

3.1 External and internal enablers

In Denmark, the informants expressed the experience that society is changing. They described engineering as a field in the midst of a change in which more employees will work as consultants in smaller enterprises rather than as employees of large companies. This, in turn, requires that engineers be trained to handle this type of employment. The community in general has been aware of this change for at least the last 5–10 years, and a number of promotional activities have been launched during this period, including activities and competitions organised by various associations not related to the university. The informants also expressed a willingness to support the competence shift that needs to be achieved in order to successfully adapt to this change at government level. For instance, there has been funding for projects that can be applied for by individual teachers or teams of teachers in

order to improve entrepreneurial and enterprise education. There have also been opportunities to apply for larger contributions that could be used to support broader changes in university education. Private donations were also mentioned as a basis for strengthening entrepreneurial education at universities.

In Japan, the informants gave a somewhat contradictory picture of the approach to implementing entrepreneurship education. On one hand, Japan has a strong desire to become more entrepreneurial, that is, to be a country where new ideas are developed and where new enterprises can start up. On the other hand, Japanese culture maintains in rather strong terms that it is almost impossible for a person to succeed after having failed, which means that in practise it is more favourable for engineers to work in the same company for the entirety of their careers. The informants expressed that companies would like engineers to develop more intrapreneurial skills; that is, companies would like EEs to teach future engineers to play entrepreneurial roles within the company and to have the ability to develop new ideas that strengthen the company. As a result of the Japanese way of looking at career life, it is not really important to educate students in entrepreneurial skills and enterprise at the university level. In the future, this can be done at the companies themselves. The informants said that UT may be in a special position, because UT students quickly and easily get jobs at large, respectable companies. Therefore, the importance of having entrepreneurial skills might be more prominent in the context of a smaller university.

The government supports initiatives like EDGE-Global and Entrepreneur-Dojo, which are global venture activities in which engineering students can participate. The problem with these activities and competitions is that they do not give university credit and are therefore seen as less attractive by the students.

In Korea, there is strong external pressure to develop entrepreneurship and innovation competencies in engineering education. Industry has influenced this process by exerting strong pressure to improve this part of engineering education, which in turn has prompted the government to see entrepreneurship education as very important. The informants described government support for student venture competitions and projects designed to strengthen engineering education as such. In South Korea, there are also some mechanisms of direct control. In the accreditation process for engineering education, universities have to show that they offer courses on entrepreneurial skills as capstone design courses. There are also upcoming plans for the government to link funding of research based on the presence or absence of entrepreneurship and innovation education, often referred to as capstone design courses, in which social issues are dealt with in teams, together with industry/society.

The Swedish informants expressed disappointment regarding the development of entrepreneurial and enterprise education. The topic has been on the agenda for many years, but without being lifted to the next level in engineering education. There is undoubtedly pressure from industry and other associations, as is evidenced by the many activities—such as competitions for

students—that are supported by companies or associations. Swedish industry also sees intrapreneurship as an important part of the development of those skills, which means that there is a desire and a need for these kinds of skills within the companies.

A popular initiative funded by a private foundation in Stockholm, the Stockholm School of Entrepreneurship Education, is partly devoted to engineering students from KTH but has the overall aim of strengthening entrepreneurship education for students from different areas. The informants did not see the government as directly supporting the development of entrepreneurship in engineering education, but there is authority that holds money for investing in entrepreneurship in Sweden through available research funds.

3.2 Processes within universities

At AAU, in Denmark, problem-based learning has been the basis for education for a very long time (Xiangyun et.al. 2009) This pedagogical methodology fosters some of the entrepreneurial skills to be developed over the course of the students' education career, because students work in teams with companies closely linked to their projects. Despite this fact, the informants expressed that faculty do not necessarily know how to educate students about entrepreneurship. Most faculty members have never worked outside the university, and therefore they most often lack 'real experience'. The aim at AAU is to give all engineering students the opportunity to learn entrepreneurial skills and enterprise, but the university's strategy for developing entrepreneurial competence is not yet clear. It may include hiring teachers from industry and/or training faculty already at the university. AAU has a centre for innovation, where engineering students can take elective courses in entrepreneurship, which often include learning outcomes such as competencies for developing a new idea and building a start-up company. The students frequently take these courses. The university also runs a master's programme in entrepreneurship, in which students work on, among other things, innovation ideas over a two-year period.

UT also has a centre for innovation and technology, where elective courses are offered to students, although this centre does not currently have much space available for engineering students. For engineering students, it is mandatory to take courses that contain some education in entrepreneurship and innovation, such as the courses called GMI and GMSI. For these courses, UT hires teachers with industry experience.

KU is pressured to develop capstone design courses for all engineering students, and these courses are therefore developed within the School of Engineering. No clear strategy for building up the competence among faculty was described by the informants, but the teachers of capstone design courses are now predominantly teachers with industry experience. KU has a centre for innovation, which is used to pursue entrepreneurial activities. The Business School offers elective courses for all students in the area of innovation and entrepreneurship. It has been difficult for engineering students to enter these courses (because the Business School has to prioritise its own students), so

the Business School now offers two courses devoted exclusively to engineering students.

As in Denmark, at Sweden's KTH, no legislation makes it mandatory to teach entrepreneurship in engineering-education programmes. But the external forces have led to the development of a master's programme in entrepreneurship and innovation. There is also a link to the Stockholm School of Entrepreneurship, where engineering students can take elective courses in this field. Enthusiastic professors, with support from management, have also initiated projects like the Open Lab, where students work in interdisciplinary teams on real-life problems, or the Global Development Hub, where teachers and students work on problems in developing countries together with students and faculty in the relevant countries. In those projects, there are elements of faculty training with designed courses for faculty on how to teach entrepreneurship.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

This study shows that the driving forces for developing entrepreneurship education vary across the four countries. It is also plausible that these differences have led to the different approaches/strategies taken by each EEI.

An important area of difference is how much pressure is put on the universities from the surrounding society and how this pressure is expressed. Figure 2 shows an estimated degree of pressure directly controlling the university and, on the other hand, if they are more indirectly governing by promoting activities. The figure shows that in the development of entrepreneurship education, both Korea and Denmark experience strong pressure from society as well as relatively strong support from government and other actors. Korea stands out as the country where there is also direct pressure on engineering education; the government partially controls the presence of entrepreneurship education in the form of capstone design courses. In Sweden and Japan, social pressure seems to be somewhat weaker than in the other two countries, although there are similar activities supported by governments and authorities to a lesser extent.

Figure 2. External pressure to develop entrepreneurship education.
DK = Denmark, J = Japan, K = South Korea, S = Sweden

We argue that the different approaches taken at the different EEIs are related to what kind of working force is or has been involved in the processes of developing entrepreneurship education (see Figure 3). In the two Nordic countries, the development of entrepreneurship education in the universities has relied very much on enthusiastic faculty members who believe in its importance. This might be due to the relatively long history of having entrepreneurial skills and enterprise on the educational agenda.

In the countries where we find strong pressure from society, we also see a high degree of involvement from people in industry. This is also true for Japan. Sweden stands out as the country that has come the furthest in the planning of developing the faculty in charge, even though this does not seem to be a well-defined strategic plan.

Figure 3. Persons involved in the work of entrepreneurship education. D = Denmark, J = Japan, K = South Korea, S = Sweden

In conclusion, this study indicates that two of the universities, AU and KU, are working harder than the other two to ready themselves and their students for important changes in how engineers work—changes that will necessitate a broader competence in entrepreneurial skills and enterprise. The other two EEIs, KTH and UT, seem to be aware of the important changes on the horizon, but they are not making proactive attempts to change engineering education accordingly.

These differences may depend partly on the country in which the EEI operates, but the differences may also depend on the characteristics of the EEI itself. Potentially crucial factors are the size of the university, its ranking, and whether it is a private or state university. We will investigate these factors more deeply in our next study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Blanchflower, D. G., & Oswald, A. J. (1998). Entrepreneurship and the youth labour market problem: a report for the OECD. *Report to OECD, Paris. November.*
- [2] Broady, D. (1999), Det svenska hos ramfaktorteorin, *Pedagogisk Forskning i Sverige: 4:1*, pp. 111–121
- [3] Ministeriet for Videnskab, Teknologi og Udvikling. Økonomi- og Erhvervsministeriet. Undervisningsministeriet. Kulturministeriet. (2010) *Strategi for uddannelse i entreprenørskab.*

- [4] Regeringskansliet. (2009) Strategi för entreprenörskap inom utbildningsområdet. *Stockholm*.
- [5] Shane, S., & Venkataraman, S. (2000). The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. *Academy of management review*, 25(1), 217-226.
- [6] Skolverket. 2015. "Skapa och våga. Om entreprenörskap i skolan." 15:1434. Stockholm
- [7] Xiangyun, D, de Graaff, E. and Kolmos, A, eds. (2009) Research on PBL Practice in Engineering Education. Rotterdam: Sense Publishers. 225pp. ISBN 978-90-8790-930-7